

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable 6.2

**Stakeholder Engagement Recommendations
for Future Key Mission R&I Core Activities**

Report including recommendations to enhance stakeholder
engagement in upcoming key Mission Research and
Innovation Actions

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Executive Summary

The Mission 'Restoring our Ocean and Waters by 2030' (hereafter 'the Mission') is one of the 5 European Commission's Missions committed to significantly enhancing the health and sustainability of oceans, seas, and inland waters. Its goals are aligned with EU strategies, focusing on protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems, preventing pollution, and fostering a sustainable blue economy that is carbon-neutral and circular.

Prep4Blue is dedicated to developing a cooperative network driving societal transformation, enhancing public knowledge and participation in sustainable management of oceans and waters. Through desktop studies and surveys, it has formed effective strategies for Stakeholder Engagement, in line with the Mission's objectives. This research led to the comprehensive Stakeholder Engagement guidelines (D6.1- Stakeholder engagement guidelines, including toolkit), focusing on optimal ways to identify, map, and engage stakeholders, consistent with the European Commission's Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters. Based on these guidelines, Prep4Blue experts crafted a concept note (Annex 8.2) which depicts a stakeholder engagement strategy for the Mission, aiming to actively involve, connect, and empower stakeholders, facilitating interaction and collaboration across the lighthouse areas. Furthermore, to aid in the identification and mapping of stakeholders, the Prep4Blue project developed the WaveLinks tool as part of the WaveLinks web platform (<https://wavelinks.eu/>). This tool encompasses a database of organizations participating in projects related to the Mission, serving as a baseline for stakeholder identification. It enables users to visualize, search, and filter this database, thereby facilitating effective stakeholder engagement.

The concept note and the tool were fundamental in organising the "StakeHolders2cO-design" co-design workshop in Brussels on the 17th of October 2023. This workshop engaged key Mission stakeholders and stakeholder engagement experts to enhance the strategy document. From this collaborative effort, a set of targeted recommendations to enhance stakeholder engagement in upcoming key Mission Research and Innovation Actions, which represents the main scope of this Deliverable, were formulated.

It is important to note that Prep4Blue is in the process of developing a tool to support stakeholder mapping in the context of stakeholder engagement, along with identifying relevant methods for engaging stakeholders within the Mission framework (accessible at <https://wavelinks.eu/>). Consequently, this Concept Note should be viewed as a dynamic document that will continue to evolve as Prep4Blue progresses. It will incorporate feedback from participants in the Mission projects and other users of the tool, with the final version set to be delivered in 2025, at the end of the 2022-2025 'development and piloting' phase 1.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and in this document.

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
P4B	Prep4Blue
(the) Mission	Mission 'Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030' / Mission Ocean and Waters
LH(s)	Lighthouse(s)
SH(s)	Stakeholder(s)
SHenG	Stakeholder(s) engagement
SHEM	Stakeholder Engagement Methods
SHES	Stakeholder Engagement Strategy
D6.1	Stakeholder engagement guidelines, including toolkit
WP(s)	Work Package(s)
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
PESTEL	PEST (Political, Economic, Socio-cultural and Technological) analysis
EC	European Commission

1 Introduction

Missions represent a novel component within the Horizon Europe programme, designed to address significant societal issues through comprehensive solutions. In 2021, the programme initiated the execution of five Missions themes: Restoring our Ocean and Waters by 2030, Adapting to Climate Change, Tackling Cancer, Developing Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities, and Enhancing Soil Health and Food. The Mission titled 'Restoring our Ocean and Waters by 2030' (hereafter 'the Mission') is dedicated to markedly enhancing the health and sustainability of oceans, seas, as well as coastal and inland waters. It seeks to accomplish this by focusing on the following goals:

- Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030;
- Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil;
- Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.

The Missions' initiative is a dynamic programme that integrates innovative technological, social, business, and governance solutions to foster new forms of cooperation and public engagement. Going beyond traditional research, it incorporates novel governance and outreach methods, encouraging involvement from diverse stakeholders across EU countries and sectors. The Mission adopts a holistic approach, blending technological progress with social and business innovation, and emphasises policy and community engagement. It particularly focuses on empowering citizens, especially youth, to participate in co-designing, implementing, and monitoring its activities, enhancing public awareness and education.

As a platform for deliberative democratic decision-making, the Mission enables citizens to actively shape Europe's future in sustainable aquatic resource management and contribute to transformative projects like the Mission lighthouses. It promotes citizen involvement through social innovation and stewardship, potentially involving the European Solidarity Corps for voluntary activities. The Mission commits to leveraging social innovation across all stages, ensuring sustainable ocean and water use. Additionally, it aims to boost public understanding and engagement through education, training, and citizen science campaigns, in collaboration with Member States, building on the EU's efforts in ocean literacy to foster a well-informed, actively participating public in aquatic resource management.

The Prep4Blue project (P4B), funded under the EU Horizon Europe programme, is a three-year initiative setting the scene for co-creating and co-implementing the research and innovation required to achieve the objectives of the Mission. It involves multiple work packages (WPs), each with specific goals and strategies.

WP3, titled 'Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters,' is dedicated to fostering social innovation and stewardship of oceans and waters. It focuses on mapping citizen roles in stewardship, engaging volunteers through the European Solidarity Corps, and developing a dynamic 'Toolbox' to facilitate and monitor citizen participation. This toolbox provides a structured approach for enhancing citizen participation, including theoretical background, participation typology, and practical advice for organising workshops and co-production of knowledge. It also incorporates strategies for Ocean Literacy, emphasising sustainable practices and responsible citizenship. Additionally, WP3 establishes

Citizen Assemblies and a Community of Practice, supported by resources like a Citizen Science Database, to deepen citizen engagement in scientific activities and participatory innovations.

WP6, named 'Stakeholder Engagement: Strategy, Connectivity and Capacity Building,' aims to develop a multidisciplinary, multi-stakeholder approach, involving industry, public authorities, academia, and civil society organisations. It adopts the 'Penta-Helix Model,' which includes the natural environment in knowledge production and innovation processes. WP6 focuses on co-producing knowledge, building capacities for stakeholder assemblies, and ensuring inclusive co-design, development, implementation, and monitoring of sustainable ocean and water management solutions.

Furthermore, the Mission supports education and training activities, citizen science campaigns, and leverages arts, media, and culture to enhance public connection and engagement with ocean and waters. WP6 dedicates specific tasks to develop capacity-building activities, including virtual training resources, and establishes a community of practice among partners. It also focuses on identifying the capacity and skills needed to achieve the Mission's targets by 2030, integrating insights from all work packages and facilitating thinktank activities across different geographic areas.

Prep4Blue is dedicated to creating a cooperative network that drives societal transformation, enhancing public knowledge and participation in the sustainable management of oceans and waters. In pursuit of this goal, the project undertook a desktop study and multiple surveys to gather effective strategies, methods, and tools for Stakeholder Engagement, aligned with the Mission's objectives. This research led to the development of a comprehensive set of Stakeholder Engagement guidelines (D6.1 - Stakeholder engagement guidelines, including toolkit). These guidelines focus on the optimal ways to identify, map, and engage stakeholders in line with the goals of the European Commission's Mission Ocean and Waters across all four lighthouses. Based on these guidelines, Prep4Blue experts crafted a concept note (Annex 8.2) for a "stakeholder engagement strategy for the Mission Oceans and Water." This strategy outlines approaches to actively involve, connect, and empower stakeholders, facilitating interaction, collaboration, and information sharing within and across the lighthouse-based areas.

The concept note has served as a fundamental document for the organisation of a co-design workshop titled "Stakeholders2cO-design - Towards impactful stakeholder engagement in the Mission Ocean and Waters," held on October 17, 2023, in Brussels, Belgium (Annex 8.1). This workshop, organized by Blue Cluster in collaboration with the CPMR, involved key stakeholders of the Mission, as well as experts in stakeholder engagement methods, with the aim of enhancing the strategy document. Experts were specifically asked to address some specific aspects of Stakeholder engagement for the deployment of the strategy within the Mission's contexts: thanks to their contributions, a set of recommendations for future key mission R&I core activities were formulated and are presented at the conclusion of this deliverable.

This document, thus, serves as a critical resource for projects under the Mission Ocean's Work Programme. It provides a structured and tested framework for stakeholder engagement, offering insights and methodologies that can be adapted and applied to various project contexts. By leveraging the guidelines (D6.1) and the recommendations outlined in this deliverable, other projects can effectively engage a wide range of stakeholders, fostering a collaborative environment that is conducive to achieving the ambitious objectives of the Mission Ocean and Waters.

2 Recommendation for the Vision and Objectives of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy for Future Key Mission R&I Core Activities

2.1 Vision

VISION

A collaborative ecosystem is set where stakeholders are actively engaged, connected, and empowered to drive forward the Mission of restoring the health of our oceans and waters by 2030.

A baseline Vision inspiring the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (SHES) should be rooted in the principles of dynamism, inclusivity, and sustainability, recognising the importance of involving a wide array of stakeholders in the Mission. Central to this vision is the concept of active and regular engagement through dialogues, collaborative governance, and adaptive management. By doing so, the diverse interests and needs of stakeholders are not just heard, but actively addressed. This approach is about creating channels for continuous communication – forums, data sharing platforms – that align with national and regional priorities while allowing for real-time feedback. Transparency, effective communication, and conflict resolution are key pillars in maintaining positive, long-term relationships with all stakeholders. The SHES should go beyond mere engagement, envisioning training, workshops, recognition, and collaborative projects, especially in the private sector, to foster sustainable practices. At the heart of the SHES should be placed the commitment to environmental sustainability, economic prosperity, and community involvement, aiming to create a cohesive society that optimally benefits from ecosystem services, energy, and food supply. This could be complemented by participatory governance, ensuring that citizens and stakeholders are not just participants, but co-creators in this journey.

To this end, the introduction of the Mission Lighthouses as local business and citizen engagement hubs, alongside a digital ocean and water knowledge system, reflects a forward-thinking approach. This not only enhances the understanding and forecasting of hydrosphere health but also promotes broad societal engagement. Furthermore, the set-up of the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP Ocean) plays a pivotal role in realising the vision of creating a collaborative ecosystem: it serves as a central hub for mission monitoring, progress tracking, and integrating actions by Mission partners facilitating further collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders.

The Stakeholder Engagement Strategy should also empower stakeholders through deliberative democracy, social innovation, and citizen science, activating their role in driving transitions while embodying the principle that no community should be left behind. This vision is not static; it evolves with the progress of the Mission Ocean, and Waters, remaining open to incorporating new stakeholder engagement methods. Its alignment with international governance norms and a focus on digital engagement ensure that it is not only relevant to current challenges but also responsive to emerging global trends and stakeholder needs.

2.2 Long-Term Objective

OBJECTIVE

Fostering an inclusive and participatory governance approach, promoting active engagement and collaboration among diverse stakeholders - such as governments, environmental organisations, industry leaders, local communities, scientists, and citizens - in the co-design and co-implementation of solutions for restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems.

The long-term objective of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy should be guided by a transformative approach rooted in the principle of fostering an inclusive and participatory governance model: the SHES is called to encompass a wide spectrum of stakeholders – governments, environmental organisations, industry leaders, local communities, scientists, and citizens – all united under its shared vision.

Central to the Mission is the innovative concept of 'promoting basin-wide cooperation'. This is embodied through the establishment of 'Lighthouses' across major European sea and river basins. These Lighthouses, serving as the main implementation vehicles in the initial phase, are not just physical entities but should be envisioned as dynamic communities. They represent a confluence of diverse stakeholders from different regions and countries, collectively pledging towards Mission's goals.

Integral to this approach is the facilitation of research and innovation. The Mission backs scalable and replicable research activities that are not just innovative but also impactful, covering a wide array of solutions - technological, business, social, and governance. These initiatives align with the Mission's objectives, driving towards environmental goals. Recognising the necessity of broadening the impact, SHES should emphasise the scaling up of successful projects through a collective approach to problem-solving, ensuring that the benefits of one project ripple across many.

In parallel, the development of a comprehensive digital knowledge system is crucial. This system, focusing on environmental and biodiversity monitoring, is designed to enhance stakeholders' understanding and ability to monitor and forecast the health of aquatic systems. This digital backbone is pivotal in supporting informed decision-making and engaging stakeholders in the management and protection of aquatic ecosystems.

Public engagement and awareness form the cornerstone of the Mission. SHES should champion deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices to mobilise public support, engage citizens, and foster a sense of shared responsibility and collective action towards restoration goals. Collecting stakeholders' perceptions and stories ensures a holistic understanding of the impacts of actions taken, deepening the connection between the Mission and its stakeholders.

A significant emphasis should also be placed on knowledge outreach, particularly towards citizens and schoolchildren. Educating these groups about the importance and impact of the Mission is crucial for fostering broader community awareness and involvement. To this end, citizen science and marine educational initiatives are integral, involving the public in scientific research and education, thus bridging the gap between science and society.

The Mission addresses the current sectoral governance of marine and coastal areas: SHES should aim for an integrated and coordinated approach. This involves targeting a wide range of agencies and

demonstrating strong connections with local management councils, water bodies, and natural parks. This linkage ensures that initiatives are grounded in local realities and needs.

The SHES also involves stakeholders in regionalising future scenarios related to conservation, restoration, and sustainable harvesting in specific marine and transitional waters, considering various PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal) factors¹. Inclusion of sea-users, local authorities, management authorities, and NGOs highlights the breadth and inclusivity of the stakeholder engagement approach, addressing diverse needs and perspectives.

Furthermore, SHES aims to establish synergies with other citizen engagement activities globally, like the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science and the EU Green Deal. The Mission's objectives need to be promoted among all relevant stakeholder groups, tailoring engagement activities to local needs and contexts.

In conclusion, SHES long-term objective should recall the importance of collaboration and co-creation but also the need for integrated approaches that combine local insights with broader governance structures. A multifaceted strategy is essential for addressing the complex challenges of restoring oceans and waters, ensuring every stakeholder's voice is heard, and every effort contributes to the collective goal of ecological restoration and sustainability.

2.3 Specific Objectives of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

From the Vision and the Long-Term Objective here above, a list of specific objectives for the SHES can be designed to create a robust framework for stakeholder engagement, ensuring that all parties are not only involved but also feel connected and empowered throughout the process, namely:

- 1. Engaging Stakeholders - To create a dynamic and interactive environment where stakeholders are not just passive recipients of information but active contributors to the Mission evolution and success.**
 - **Establishment of Regular Communication Channels:** This involves the creation of specialised platforms designed to facilitate ongoing and transparent communication with all involved stakeholders. These platforms serve as an instrument for ensuring that stakeholders are kept abreast of updates and developments, fostering a culture of open information sharing.
 - **Organisation of Stakeholder Workshops and Meetings:** This aspect focuses on the regular organisation of workshops, meetings, and forums. These gatherings are pivotal in bringing stakeholders together, providing a space for meaningful dialogue and the exchange of ideas. They serve as a forum for stakeholders to voice their thoughts, share insights, and collaboratively explore various aspects of the Mission.
 - **Development of Tailored Engagement Programmes:** In recognition of the diverse nature of stakeholders, this strategy involves crafting specific engagement programmes. These programmes are designed to cater to the distinct interests, concerns, and potential contributions of different stakeholder groups, ensuring that each group's unique perspective is acknowledged and incorporated into the broader Mission framework.
 - **Implementation of Collaborative Decision-Making Processes:** This involves integrating stakeholders into the heart of decision-making processes. By utilising collaborative platforms

¹PESTLE analysis (also known as PESTEL analysis) is a tool used for understanding the macro-environmental factors that impact an organization, company, or industry. This analysis focuses on Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors in the external environment, and is utilized to identify threats and weaknesses which are then used in a SWOT analysis.

and the principles of deliberative democracy, stakeholders are not merely informed about decisions but are actively involved in shaping them. This approach ensures that decision-making is a collective and inclusive process.

- **Facilitation of Stakeholder Feedback and Input:** Central to this approach is the establishment of systems designed for the collection and integration of stakeholder feedback into the Mission's implementation phases. These systems are crucial for ensuring that the insights, concerns, and suggestions of stakeholders are not only heard but are also instrumental in guiding the Mission's trajectory.
2. **Connecting Stakeholders - To create a robust, interactive, and cohesive network of diverse stakeholders.**
- **Fostering Networks Among Diverse Stakeholder Groups:** This initiative is centred on nurturing networking opportunities that serve as a catalyst for bringing together stakeholders from varied sectors and geographical regions. The objective is to create a vibrant community where stakeholders can engage in collaborative endeavours and share knowledge. This networking not only facilitates the exchange of ideas but also fosters a sense of unity among diverse groups, each bringing its unique perspective and expertise to the table.
 - **Cultivating Partnership Opportunities:** The focus here is on identifying and nurturing opportunities for partnerships among stakeholders. This involves orchestrating scenarios where entities such as governmental bodies, private organisations, environmental groups, and others can collaborate on joint projects or engage in co-funding initiatives. These partnerships are pivotal in pooling resources and expertise, thereby amplifying the impact of individual efforts.
 - **Utilising Digital Platforms to Bridge Geographical Gaps:** Recognising the geographical spread of stakeholders, this strategy emphasises the use of digital tools and platforms to bridge distances. By leveraging the power of technology, stakeholders who are geographically dispersed can connect, collaborate, and contribute seamlessly, ensuring that physical distance is no barrier to effective cooperation and engagement.
 - **Organising Multi-Stakeholder Convergences:** This entails the planning and execution of various forms of gatherings – conferences, seminars, and workshops – that assemble stakeholders from different spheres. These events are designed not just as platforms for discussion but as melting pots where common goals and challenges can be deliberated upon. Such gatherings are instrumental in forging a sense of community and shared purpose among stakeholders from disparate backgrounds.
 - **Championing Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** In this approach, there is a deliberate effort to encourage and facilitate collaborations across different disciplines. By bringing together stakeholders from varied fields like science, industry, and governance, the strategy aims to create a rich, multidisciplinary tapestry of ideas and solutions. This interdisciplinary collaboration is crucial in addressing complex challenges in a holistic and integrated manner, drawing upon the strengths and insights of each field.
3. **Empowering Stakeholders – To enable stakeholders towards more active, informed, and influential role in Mission's projects and initiatives.**
- **Facilitating Educational Empowerment:** At the core of this initiative is the provision of a variety of educational opportunities, including workshops, training sessions, and a rich array of educational resources. These platforms are designed to significantly enhance the knowledge

and skill sets of stakeholders. The goal is to empower stakeholders to not only understand the complexities of the Mission but also to actively contribute to it in a meaningful way.

- ***Nurturing Stakeholder-Led Ventures:*** *This aspect focuses on cultivating a supportive environment where stakeholder-led initiatives can thrive. By offering necessary resources and expert guidance, the strategy encourages stakeholders to bring their unique ideas and projects to life. This support reflects a commitment to harnessing the innovative potential and unique perspectives of stakeholders.*
- ***Celebrating Stakeholder Achievements:*** *A key component of empowerment is the recognition and celebration of the contributions and achievements of stakeholders. By acknowledging their efforts and celebrating their successes, the strategy aims to foster a sense of appreciation and motivation, encouraging continued participation and deepening commitment.*
- ***Ensuring Information Accessibility:*** *This element emphasises the importance of providing stakeholders with easy access to relevant data, information, and resources. By ensuring that stakeholders can readily obtain the information they need, the strategy empowers them to make informed decisions and contributions, enhancing their involvement and effectiveness in Mission-related activities.*
- ***Promoting Autonomy in Mission Participation:*** *The strategy also involves fostering stakeholders' autonomy in various aspects of the Mission. This approach allows stakeholders to take ownership and lead specific initiatives or components, providing them with a sense of independence and responsibility. It is a move towards empowering stakeholders to shape the direction and outcomes of the Mission in areas where their expertise and insights are most valuable.*

Table 2. Table of potential contributions from Prep4Blue to the Strategy for Stakeholders Engagement

POTENTIAL CONTRIBUTION FROM PREP4BLUE	
Incorporating these Prep4Blue (P4B) outcomes into the SHES operational framework can further support a comprehensive, inclusive, and effective stakeholder engagement process, leveraging innovative tools and methodologies for maximum impact.	
P4B Outcome	SHES Application
Aligning EC International, National, and Regional Initiatives (PREP4BLUE - SO1.1 & SO1.2): mechanisms for cooperation and knowledge exchange.	Build and strengthen stakeholder networks, enhance collaboration across different sectors and regions.
Communication and Dissemination Strategy (PREP4BLUE- SO2.1 & SO2.2): Mission Narrative and Communication Strategy.	Establish regular communication channels using these narratives and strategies, recognise and celebrate stakeholder contributions.
Active Citizen Participation (PREP4BLUE - SO3.1 & SO3.2): strategies for citizen assemblies and participation methodologies.	Tailor engagement programs to be inclusive, implement collaborative decision-making processes, provide educational and training opportunities.
Supporting Effective Knowledge Management (PREP4BLUE - SO4.1, SO4.2 & SO4.3): Digital solutions for knowledge management.	Facilitate stakeholders' feedback and input, leverage digital platforms for networking, enable access to information and resources.
Creating an Enabling Environment for Investments (PREP4BLUE - SO5.1 & SO5.2: Business and governance models, guides on funding mechanisms.	Create partnership opportunities, support stakeholder-led initiatives.
Developing Measures for Impactful Stakeholder Engagement (PREP4BLUE - SO6.1 & SO6.2): Capacity-building for stakeholder engagement, methodologies for stakeholders' assemblies.	Host multi-stakeholder events, promote interdisciplinary collaboration, facilitate stakeholder autonomy in projects.

3 Concepts

The Mission Oceans and Waters adeptly intertwines key concepts—co-design, co-implementation, co-development, co-monitoring, collaborative research, collaborative governance, and deliberative democracy—within its Stakeholder Engagement framework. This strategic integration is pivotal to achieving the Mission's ambitious goals of aquatic environment restoration and preservation by 2030. These features and expectations highlight the Mission's commitment to participatory and democratic processes, citizen engagement, and the use of technology and innovation to achieve its objectives.

Underpinning all these efforts is the Mission's commitment to collaborative governance and deliberative democracy, establishing platforms for stakeholder engagement and co-creation at various levels. This governance structure ensures that the Mission's initiatives are both inclusive and representative of the stakeholders they serve.

By 2025, the Mission aims to have applied these principles effectively, particularly in leveraging deliberative democracy for co-design and co-implementation. The goal extends to developing

participatory governance frameworks and expanding citizen science campaigns. By 2030, the vision is to fully engage European stakeholders in ocean and water preservation, utilising participatory means to foster public mobilisation and education. The Mission's integrated approach in its Stakeholder Engagement framework is key to realizing these goals, ensuring a sustainable and inclusive future for Europe's aquatic environments.

Based on the "Mission Implementation Plan" (European Commission. (2021).) document, here are the definitions and explanations for the specified concepts that emphasise a participatory, collaborative, and integrative approach to ocean and water governance, research, and solution development, involving citizens, stakeholders, and various sectors in decision-making and implementation processes.

3.1 Co-design process

Co-design, as a cornerstone of the Mission's approach, blends the diverse expertise of scientists, local communities, and other stakeholders, ensuring that everyone actively shapes decisions. This inclusive process not only fosters a deep sense of ownership, commitment, and trust among all involved, but also results in the creation of strategies that are finely tailored to meet the unique challenges of each context. By synthesising different perspectives, co-design ensures smoother, conflict-free execution of plans. Specifically, in the Mission's framework, co-design is about collaboratively crafting solutions and strategies for the sustainable use of oceans and waters, with a strong emphasis on social innovation. It leverages the concept of citizen stewardship, engaging stakeholders not just in the design but also in the implementation of transformative solutions, thereby ensuring that these strategies are both effective and deeply resonant with the needs and aspirations of the communities they serve.

3.2 Co-implementation (process)

Co-implementation, on the other hand, underscores shared responsibility in actioning these strategies. Stakeholders jointly navigate the path, allowing for real-time adjustments, efficient resource utilisation, and mutual learning. Co-implementation is about jointly executing these transformative solutions that have been co-designed. This process involves empowering and activating stakeholders to take action, promoting practices of social innovation, and leveraging collaborative efforts in the sustainable management of aquatic resources.

3.3 Collaborative research

Collaborative research, underpinned by robust, comprehensive scientific data, harnesses the collective expertise of diverse stakeholders, offering holistic insights into our oceans, seas, and waters. Such a joint approach not only accelerates discoveries by pooling resources and knowledge but also fosters trust, ensuring cohesive strategy execution. The enriched perspective that emerges from this collaboration can lead to innovative solutions, broader impacts on policy and public opinion, and a continuous refinement of research based on evolving on-ground realities. This entails improving cooperation across various sectors, regions, and countries for the sharing and integration of information. In the context of marine biodiversity, collaborative research aims to widen the knowledge base, develop better monitoring, and create new methodologies.

Co-design and co-implementation processes are integral part of the Collaborative approach/research. This shared journey amplifies the Mission's impact, ensuring a sustainable and inclusive approach to preserving our oceans, seas, and waters by 2030. By integrating these processes, the vision

emphasizes a comprehensive, collaborative effort from concept to realization, where every participant is both a designer and implementer of the future.

3.4 Co-development (of solutions)

Co-development, similar to co-design, involves stakeholders in the solution development phase for sustainable ocean and water use. It parallels co-design, emphasising social innovation, citizen stewardship, and collective strategy development for the sustainable management of aquatic resources.

3.5 Co-monitoring (of solutions)

Co-monitoring is the joint oversight and tracking of developed solutions for sustainable ocean and water use. It requires continuous engagement of stakeholders to monitor the effectiveness and impact of the implemented solutions, ensuring their long-term sustainability and adaptability.

3.6 Collaborative Governance

Collaborative Governance is an integrated, participatory approach to ocean and water management. It entails continuous engagement with institutional partners and citizens, organising forums to discuss progress and objectives. This governance approach aims to create a more cohesive and participatory management system for sustainable ocean and water management.

3.7 Deliberative Democracy

Deliberative Democracy in the Mission involves applying participatory governance and establishing an EU-wide network of assemblies. This facilitates effective citizen and stakeholder involvement in the co-design and co-implementation of aquatic environment restoration solutions, ensuring that diverse voices contribute to decision-making processes.

3.8 Application of concepts

The application of co-design, co-implementation, co-development, co-monitoring, collaborative research, and deliberative democracy is intricately tied to the achievement of the operational goals for Stakeholders Engagement identified thanks to D6.1. The Deliverable emphasizes three key aspects:

- **Engaging Stakeholders:** Emphasizing collaborative governance, integrated management, and adaptive management, D6.1 advocates for creating multi-stakeholder platforms for collective decision-making. This approach, focusing on the holistic management of marine ecosystems and dynamic stakeholder integration, fosters an inclusive environment conducive to co-design and co-development processes.
- **Connecting Stakeholders:** The Deliverable highlights the significance of building interconnected networks among various stakeholder groups, including government bodies, local communities, businesses, and educational institutions. It underlines the necessity of establishing cooperative platforms and effective communication channels, essential for active stakeholder participation in decision-making, thus enriching co-implementation and collaborative research.
- **Empowering Stakeholders:** At the core of D6.1 is the empowerment of stakeholders through establishing their rights and responsibilities, promoting shared management practices, and integrating them into policy creation and execution. This empowerment ensures stakeholders'

meaningful involvement in all project phases, enhancing the effectiveness and adaptability of the entire engagement process.

The implementation of these principles starts with critical steps such as identifying and mapping stakeholders to ensure the integration of diverse and relevant perspectives. This step is crucial for setting the foundation for open communication and trust, pivotal for collaborative decision-making. In this environment, stakeholders are not just informed participants but active contributors, thereby boosting the effectiveness of co-design, co-development, and co-implementation strategies. Such proactive engagement, underpinned by these foundational elements, motivates stakeholders to take initiative, significantly enhancing the robustness of research and the adaptability of monitoring processes.

The application of the concepts outlined above, following the guidelines provided by D6.1, has led to the formulation of the specific recommendations presented in Chapter 5. The recommendations are a direct result of this comprehensive approach, providing a practical roadmap for all actors involved in the Mission Work Programme on how to engage with stakeholders within their projects.

4 The Engagement Framework in the Mission

In the Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030” a stakeholder (SH) is someone (either individual person or organisation) that has interests and/or responsibilities towards achieving the Mission’s objectives. Therefore, given the extent of the Mission, all kinds of stakeholders should be considered but this prerequisite calls for a strong effort as for their identification and mapping. To this end, Prep4Blue developed an online tool as part of the WaveLinks web platform (www.wavelinks.eu) built under the CSA projects Prep4Blue , BlueMissionBANOS and BlueMissionAA. The tool includes a database of organisations that participate on projects linked to the Mission Ocean that can be considered as a first baseline of stakeholders of the Mission. This database of stakeholders can be visualized, searched, and filtered by users of the online tool.

In a first application, Prep4Blue used the PentaHelix approach organising the SH in the database (7,624 Total Stakeholders) according to the following categories: Industry and Businesses (3,729 Stakeholders), Science (1,111 Stakeholders), Public Authorities (754 Stakeholders), Citizens/CSOs (910 Stakeholders) and Environmental Associations (244 Stakeholders).

Figure 1. Percentage of Stakeholders per PentaHelix Category

Furthermore, Prep4Blue analysed the Horizon Europe workplans 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 for identifying the general SHs to be engaged by Lighthouses (LHs) according to their specific objectives. P4B considered also the best methods for part of the goals of the Mission. These goals include enhancing awareness among stakeholders and citizens regarding the Mission's objectives, programmes, tools, and opportunities for their active participation. Additionally, the aim is to improve the accessibility of stakeholders, such as the scientific community, businesses, local and regional communities, NGOs, and others, to programmes and instruments that support the restoration, conservation, and sustainable use of oceans, seas, and waters. The outcome of this analysis resulted in the identification of specific categories for each LH, which will be further refined through collaboration with the basin CSAs.

Table 3. Stakeholders (categories) to be involved per lighthouse and/or objective in the Mission Work programme 2021-2022

EUROPEAN BLUE PARKS	DANUBE	ATLANTIC / ARCTIC	MED	BALTIC / NORTH SEA
LONG TERM MANAGEMENT OF SOLUTIONS ✓ Citizen participation, European Volunteer Corps and Mission Citizen Assemblies, Ocean literacy networks, consumer involvement ✓ NGOs for conservation, raising awareness, education ✓ Regional and local authorities, policy makers. Sometimes national and transnational levels are required ✓ Local business communities, in particular SMEs, investors and other business stakeholders → Business models for generating revenue from the solutions ✓ Engage 3-5 'associated regions' to showcase the feasibility, replicability and scale up of the solutions, enable them to follow closely the project and provide them with technical assistance to build capacity SYNERGIES: Engage with other projects				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land & Sea use planning decision-makers MPAs managers Conservationists Natura 2000, National Parks, Biosphere Reserves Business stakeholders (fishing, aquaculture, tourist sectors, wind farms, transports, oil companies...) Networks of Parks, ex. MedPAN Seaweed restoration initiatives and algae farming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste water treatment plants Water agencies NGOs Conservationists Managers of protected areas National/local authorities for natural risk prevention Farming Territorial concertation experts ICPDR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water treatment Ports, cities, urban planners Risk prevention authorities Business stakeholders (Fishing, aquaculture, tourist sectors, wind farms, transports, oil companies...) EU Outermost Regions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ports, cities, urban planners Land owners, soil managers Water managers, river management authorities Water treatment Recycling Risk prevention authorities Business stakeholders (fishing, aquaculture, tourist sectors, transports, oil companies, recycling...) Diplomacy North/South 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fishing, aquaculture, tourist sectors, wind farms, energy industry, transports, oil companies Consumers Policy makes

Analysing the SH Database using such specific categories and related keywords allows for the initial visualisation of an SH Ecosystem for each LH. This process enables the refinement of PentaHelix categories by focusing on SHs that align with the unique goals of LHs (forming sub-groups). These sub-groups can be quantified based on the data gathered by Wavelinks and linked to a PentaHelix category for sizing purposes (Table 4)². It is possible both to visualize the relevance, in terms of number of SH, of both the PentaHelix groups and thematic subgroups for each LH (Figure 2).

Table 4. Number of stakeholders in the Wavelinks database identified per SH category and sub-groups.

SH Categories	SH Sub-Groups	SH Number
Associations (Environmental NGOs)	Environmental NGOs	42
Citizens/CSOs	Consumer Associations	3
Industry	Business stakeholders - aquaculture	18
Industry	Business stakeholders - fishing	23

² The data in Wavelinks did not allow for the categorization of all stakeholders, or for some of them, none of the sub-groups defined in Table 3 could be attributed.

Industry	Business stakeholders - oil companies	18
Industry	Business stakeholders - other blue economy sectors	616
Industry	Business stakeholders - tourist sector	7
Industry	Business stakeholders - transports	28
Industry	Business stakeholders - wind and energy farms	116
Industry	Business stakeholders - Other business actors	2276
Industry	Farming, Agriculture and Food production	92
Industry	Technology and Innovation providers	88
Knowledge Sector	Research and Academia	339
Other	Other actors dealing with conservation	14
Other	Communications and Media	20
Other	Education and Training	54
Other	Land Owners, soil managers	300
Other	Protected Areas	209
Other	Recycling and Circular Economy	12
Other	Waste Water Treatments	5
Public Authorities	Policy Makers	251
Public Authorities	Ports, Cities, urban planners	30
Public Authorities	Risk prevention Authorities	8
Public Authorities	River Management Authorities	2
Public Authorities	Water Agencies and Management	10
Public Authorities	Uncategorized	3043

Figure 2. Tree map on stakeholders per SH category and sub-group

Thus, each PentaHelix category and sub-group can be aligned with the LHs, focusing on their importance to related specific objectives (sub-groups) as discussed in the desktop study mentioned earlier. This approach provides a comprehensive view of various SHs, identified using the tool, which each LH should target to enhance awareness and participation (Figure 3). Additionally, it gives further targets for dissemination and scaling up of programmes and instruments dedicated to the restoration, conservation, and sustainable use of oceans, seas, and marine environments.

Figure 3. Sankey diagrams on relevant SH categories and sub-groups per LH

Furthermore, for each stakeholder, the P4B database reports its location which can be allocated to one of the LH Basins giving an overview of their specific SH ecosystems per geo-location (Figure 4): crossing this information with the previous one about the relevance of each sub-group for the LHs, as for their specific objectives, it is also possible to visualise potentials and opportunities for collaborations between LHs in terms of Stakeholder Engagement (Figure 5) for facilitating their involvement through respective networks.

Figure 4. Venn diagrams on SH Ecosystems per LH according to their location

Figure 5. Sankey diagrams on connection between Lighthouses' SH Ecosystems

In the upcoming version of the P4B online tool, users will have the capability to enhance this data organisation by searching for stakeholders who have participated in projects related to specific keywords such as "microalgae" or "MPAs." Additionally, users can specifically search for stakeholders involved in projects linked to Objective 3 of Mission Ocean. This approach ensures that relevant stakeholders are profiled and mapped across various scales and sub-sectors, taking into account interlinkages based on thematic similarities and previous collaborations. Leveraging the database and mapping functions of the tool, P4B aims to generate a comprehensive stakeholder ecosystem, inspiring new Engagement Recommendations as detailed in the subsequent chapter.

It is important to note that the tool can also assist in finding relevant methods to engage stakeholders within the context of Mission Ocean. The tool's development involved a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. Initially, EU projects mentioning stakeholder engagement methods in their project descriptions were identified using RegEx³ searches on the CORDIS database. This involved using RegEx searches to capture variations and conjugations of words such as "stakeholder," "engagement," "consultation," and "inclusion," resulting in a list of 3,783 projects.

Further refinement, employing the Latent Dirichlet Allocation topic modelling algorithm, narrowed down the projects to 650, specifically related to Mission Ocean objectives. Additionally, RegEx searches using the European Science Vocabulary contributed an extra 166 projects. The EC Portfolio and Dashboard of projects linked to Mission Ocean were also scrutinised for projects not already included in the mapping.

Subsequently, a more manual qualitative process unfolded, involving the examination of 161 deliverables on stakeholder engagement, communication, and dissemination from 65 distinct projects. This process served the dual purpose of identifying stakeholder engagement methods for the SHEM list and exploring patterns in the deliverables that could be leveraged for process automation.

Apart from scraping CORDIS for projects, efforts were made to identify Blue Balance projects applying SHEM, integrating these methods and projects into the SHEM list. Following the consolidation of the initial SHEM list through consultations with stakeholder engagement experts in PREP4BLUE, P4B

³ Regular Expression https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regular_expression

automatically established links between the identified methods and the projects in the database associated with Mission Ocean, where these methods were mentioned in project deliverables.

Table 5. Initial list of methods and how they were collected from EU projects linked to the Mission Ocean

Method	Level of engagement
Newsletter	Inform
Project website	Inform
Social media	Inform
Printed media (appearances)	Inform
Storymap (infographic website)	Inform
Media appearances (audio/video)	Inform
High-level outreach	Inform
Conferences and events	Inform/consult
Stakeholder meetings	Inform/consult
Virtual communities	Inform/consult
Real life communities or networks	Inform/consult
Open meetings/Town hall meetings	Inform/consult
Public consultation	Inform/consult
Exposition/work ateliers	Inform/consult
Survey	Consult
User group	Consult
DELPHI (meta method for questionnaires)	Consult
Regnier's Abacus (meta method for workshops)	Consult
Joint focus workshops	Consult/involve
Focus groups	Consult/involve
Semi structured interviews	Consult/involve
Role play: Actor constellation	Consult/involve
Dilemmas cafe	Consult/involve
Case studies and working groups	Consult/involve
World cafe	Consult/involve
Ecosystem Service assessment (ESA)	Consult/involve
Deliberative Mapping/Mind mapping	Involve
Online Discussions	Involve
Civic monitoring	Involve
Open Innovation - crowdsourcing	Involve
Start-up action: business plan competition	Involve
Summer/winter school	Involve/empower
Citizen Science	Involve/empower
Capacity Building	Involve/empower
Gamification	Involve/empower
Hackathon	Involve/empower

Foresight/future scenario workshops	Involve/empower
Co-creation sessions/workshops	Involve/empower
Research agenda camp – co-creation workshops	Involve/empower
Participatory Planning	Involve/empower
Webinar/web-based training	Empower
Business match-making events	Empower
Think tank	Empower
Living Labs	Empower
Action research	Empower
Participatory budgeting	Empower
Open Space Technology	Empower

These efforts have produced the aforementioned list of methods (Table 5) for engaging stakeholders. P4B anticipates that associating these methods with specific projects can serve a dual purpose: it can illustrate the practical application of these methods and assist users of the tool in finding methods that align with their projects. This linkage can also facilitate the identification of method combinations used together, as certain groups of projects may adopt similar combinations of methods. Figure 6 below illustrates how various engagement methods can be connected through the projects in which they were employed, and vice versa.

Figure 6. Example network of 3 projects using 4 engagement methods.

The interconnections between project, participant, and stakeholder method data will enable users to identify all stakeholders who have utilized a particular engagement method in the past. WaveLinks in this manner, can aid users in identifying potential stakeholders for engagement.

In the upcoming version of the SHEM online tool, we will identify stakeholders who have been involved through a specific method in previous projects, provided this information is available in the project deliverables or is inputted by users into the database. The stakeholders engaged in the past using a specific method will be showcased on the detailed page of that method.

5 Stakeholder Engagement Recommendations for Future Key Mission R&I Core Activities

- I. **Pre-Engagement Planning:** This phase is crucial for laying the groundwork for successful stakeholder engagement. It involves a deep understanding of the project's background, context, and legislative environment. This stage also emphasizes the need for early and comprehensive stakeholder mapping, resource assessment, and gap identification, ensuring that the project aligns with the objectives of the Mission and broader environmental goals.
 - a) **Background and Context Understanding:** Begin with a thorough understanding of the project's background and context, including the significance of the environmental, social, and legislative aspects pertinent to marine conservation, restoration, prevention and elimination of pollution and sustainable Blue Economy. Incorporate environmental impact assessments and stakeholder interest surveys for a more robust understanding.
 - b) **Comprehensive Stakeholder Mapping:** Employ the Penta-Helix model to identify a wide range of stakeholders, including industry, public authorities, local residents, academia, and associations. Enhance this process with data analytics tools for more accurate mapping and identification.
 - c) **Purpose, Participants, and Engagement Strategies:** Clearly define the purpose of engagement, identify the participants, and decide on the methods and timing for engagement. This involves considering different engagement methods, conflict management strategies, and the overall timing of stakeholder involvement. Introduce strategy workshops and role-playing scenarios to refine engagement methods further.
 - d) **Early Stakeholder Identification:** Recognize the importance of early stakeholder identification. This identification should be dynamic and iterative, aligning with the Mission's specific objectives and ensuring stakeholder relevance and potential long-term contributions. Leverage social media and online forums for broader stakeholder outreach.
 - e) **Historical and Legislative Context:** Acknowledge the significance of international, European, and regional conventions and legislations focused on marine pollution reduction and ecosystem conservation. Leverage support from funding programs and understand the historical context of previous projects addressing similar issues. Conduct comparative studies of similar projects and their legislative environments for deeper insights.
 - f) **Resource Access and Gap Identification:** Focus on ensuring better access to resources and more accurately identifying gaps in project planning and execution. This also

involves recognizing the need for tools, guidelines, and training in marine conservation efforts. Utilize technology like GIS for resource mapping and identification of environmental hotspots.

- g) Co-Creation and Methodological Approaches:** Initiate a co-creation process by engaging with stakeholders through interviews and other methods. Use tools and methodologies to de-risk the project before and during the co-creation phase, ensuring that the project methodologies are replicable and effectively address the project's objectives. Engage in prototype testing and pilot studies for methodological refinement.

II. Setting the Foundation: The foundation stage establishes a collaborative governance structure and prioritizes inclusivity. It emphasizes the importance of maintaining the sustainability of the project and its stakeholder community. Building credibility through transparency and trust is key to setting a strong foundation for the engagement process.

a) Preliminary actions:

- Set project ambitions and boundary conditions collaboratively. Identify stakeholders' roles in the project.
- Promote cross-cutting interdisciplinarity for effective stakeholder engagement; integrate actors and ensure the delivery of academic excellence.
- Integrate technology platforms for better coordination and communication among stakeholders.

b) Collaborative Governance:

- Establish collaborative governance, merging and interlinking governmental institutions and promoting intercommunication for more effective stakeholder engagement.
- Implement digital tools for real-time governance and stakeholder feedback.

c) Inclusivity and Credibility:

- Emphasize inclusivity in stakeholder engagement, ensuring gender and other forms of inclusivity are addressed. Prioritize transparency and trust-building to establish credibility with all stakeholders. To this end, use appropriate language, and understanding the project's context to facilitate better stakeholder collaboration.
- Establish a dedicated inclusivity committee to oversee and report on inclusivity measures.

d) Project and Action Sustainability:

- Focus on maintaining the sustainability of the project and the related community of all stakeholders.
- Incorporate sustainable development goals (SDGs) as benchmarks for project sustainability.

III. Engagement Execution: This stage involves dynamically engaging stakeholders at different phases of the project. It emphasizes the adaptability of stakeholder roles and contributions throughout the project lifecycle, ensuring continuous involvement and meaningful contribution from all parties.

a) Engagement actions:

- Use stakeholder engagement methods to raise awareness, manage risks, share best practices, and access resources.
- Introduce virtual engagement platforms for wider reach and continuous engagement.

- Engage stakeholders as equals, value all shared knowledge, and understand their varying needs.
- Address ethical issues, including intellectual property and data protection.
- Allow stakeholders the opportunity to plan their own engagement and actively participate.
- Open up methods for stakeholder engagement, explore key interests, and prioritize them.
- Plan targeted activities and account for the time and cost of stakeholder engagement.
- Maintain stakeholder interest, especially among influential stakeholders. Use co-creation methodologies such as “work benches” where clients/users and other stakeholders receive tasks and work in iterative cycles, ensuring everyone takes ownership.
- Engage specialized experts for targeted inputs.
- Ensure a joint fact-finding process to create a safe space for information exchange among experts.
- Break the project down into sections, seeking expert input for each specific area.
- Implement co-creation methodologies, ensuring stakeholders receive tasks and work in iterative cycles for shared ownership.
- Engage stakeholders by seeking their advice, soliciting their support for dissemination, and involving them in training.
- Manage challenges such as mistrust from governmental agencies, language barriers, and the difficulty of securing involvement from EU and regional organizations.
- Highlight successful engagement stories.

b) **Active Engagement in Project Phases:**

- Engage stakeholders before, during, and after the project. Prior to the project start, define concepts and identify outcomes. During the project, establish agreements for resource provision, training, capacity building, knowledge sharing, scenario development, co-designing conflict resolution, and reviewing success measurement. Post-project, focus on implementation, publicity, and promotion of results.
- Utilize social media and online communities for post-project engagement and feedback collection.

c) **Dynamic Stakeholder Roles:** Recognize and adapt to the evolving roles and contributions of stakeholders throughout the project, ensuring continuous updates and communications about these changes.

IV. Conflict Management & Resolution: Effective conflict management and resolution are critical in this phase. The focus is on developing adaptive strategies to manage and resolve conflicts, acknowledging the evolving dynamics and interests of stakeholders throughout the project.

a) **Conflict Management Actions:**

- Recognize and manage various types of stakeholder conflicts, from open to latent conflicts. To this end, implement a conflict anticipation system using predictive analytics.
- Use established methods to address cognitive, interest-based, normative, relational, need-based, process, and structural conflicts.

- Address specific challenges faced during stakeholder engagement, like initial distrust, language issues, and stakeholder fatigue.
 - Implement strategies to maintain stakeholder interest, mitigate disappointment, and address any challenges arising from diverse backgrounds and expectations.
 - b) **Adaptive Conflict Resolution:** Develop adaptive strategies for conflict resolution, understanding that stakeholder interests and dynamics may change over the course of the project.
- V. **Monitoring, Feedback & Improvement:** Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the engagement process are essential in this stage. It involves adapting engagement strategies based on feedback and identified challenges and leveraging advanced technologies for decision-making and effective management.
 - a) **Monitoring Actions:**
 - Monitor and evaluate conflicts to improve stakeholder engagement planning.
 - Focus on objectives, measure success, and demonstrate value through continuous monitoring.
 - Regularly assess the impact of stakeholder contributions to ensure alignment and effectiveness.
 - Ensure the relevance of stakeholder engagement by using understandable languages, respecting timelines, and ensuring real impact.
 - Always have a contingency plan in place to adapt to unforeseen challenges or changes.
 - Use advanced technologies like AI to manage complex trade-offs, complexities and support decision-making.
 - Constantly monitor and evaluate stakeholder engagement, ensuring alignment with project goals, and demonstrate the value of stakeholder contributions.
 - Integrate feedback loops using digital survey tools for immediate stakeholder feedback.
 - b) **Comprehensive Evaluation:** Implement a thorough monitoring and evaluation system to continuously assess stakeholder engagement effectiveness, adapting to identified gaps and challenges.
- VI. **Post-Engagement Activities:** This final phase emphasizes the importance of communicating the societal impact and value of stakeholder contributions. It also focuses on maintaining engagement and communication with stakeholders beyond the project completion to ensure sustained relationships and ongoing collaboration.
 - a) **Feedback and Societal Impact:** Provide stakeholders comprehensive feedback on the outcomes and societal impact of their contributions, using storytelling and digital media for enhanced communication.
 - b) **Ongoing Engagement and Communication:** Ensure continued engagement and communication with stakeholders post-project, fostering a sustained relationship through online community forums and other digital platforms.

6 Conclusions

The Deliverable offers a comprehensive set of Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (SHES) Recommendations designed to support stakeholder engagement in the Research and Innovation Actions of the Mission. Developed through the collaborative efforts of the Prep4Blue project, the recommendations are integrated into a unified strategy for stakeholder engagement and incorporates innovative elements like the WaveLinks tool to meaningfully and effectively involve various stakeholders.

The recommendations begin with the pre-engagement planning phase, emphasizing the importance of understanding the context and defining the purpose of engagement, along with identifying relevant stakeholders. This phase incorporates tools to de-risk the co-creation process and acknowledges the significance of international and regional conventions related to marine pollution. The foundation of the report is set by promoting interdisciplinary collaboration, integrating diverse actors to achieve academic excellence, and building trust through transparency. Moreover, the recommendations emphasize the critical role of inclusivity and societal relevance in stakeholder engagement, encouraging collaborative efforts in setting project goals.

In the engagement execution phase, the focus is on using the engagement process to raise awareness, manage risks, and share best practices. This involves treating stakeholders as equals and addressing ethical concerns, including intellectual property and data protection. The plan also involves maintaining stakeholder interest through innovative co-creation methodologies and engaging specialized experts for targeted insights. The recommendations also encompass conflict management and resolution, addressing various stakeholder conflicts using established methods. It includes strategies to manage challenges such as initial distrust and language barriers. Monitoring, feedback, and improvement form a crucial part of the deliverable, involving continuous assessment of the engagement process and the impact of stakeholder contributions. Finally, the recommendations include post-engagement activities, providing stakeholders with feedback on outcomes and emphasizing the importance of ongoing engagement and communication throughout the project lifecycle.

This Deliverable serves as a fundamental document, not only for the Mission but also for guiding current and future environmental and conservation initiatives. By establishing a dynamic and interconnected community of stakeholders, the document aims to realize the ambitious goals of the "Mission, contributing significantly to global environmental sustainability and ecological balance.

7 Bibliography

1. European Commission. (2022). *Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030*. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. ISBN: 978-92-76-46714-4, DOI: 10.2777/904515.
2. Durham E., Baker H., Smith M., Moore E. & Morgan V. (2014). *The BiodivERSA Stakeholder Engagement Hand-book*. BiodivERSA, Paris;
3. Ferguson, L., Chan, S., Santelmann, M., & Wright, M. (2016). *Stakeholder Collaborative Engagement: An annotated reference guide for scientific engagement with natural-resource practitioners*. Oregon State University, Marine Resource Management Program. <http://seagrant.oregonstate.edu/sgpubs>;
4. Singletary, L., Koebele, E., Evans, W., Copp, C. J., Hockaday, S., & Rego, J. J. (2022). *Evaluating stakeholder engagement in collaborative research: Co-producing knowledge for climate resilience*. *Socio-Ecological Practice Research*, 4, 235–249. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42532-022-00124-8>;
5. Barquet, K., Segnestam, L., & Dickin, S. (2022). *MapStakes: A tool for mapping involving and monitoring stakeholders in co-creation processes*. Stockholm Environment Institute. <https://doi.org/10.51414/sei2022.014>;
6. European Commission. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. (2023). *Baseline study for the implementation of lighthouses of the Mission 'Restore our ocean and waters by 2030': Atlantic Arctic Danube and Mediterranean lighthouses*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/34856>;
7. European Commission. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. (2023). *Baseline study for the implementation of the lighthouse in the Baltic and North Sea basins for the Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030'*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/96040>;
8. European Commission. (2021). *Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030' - Implementation plan* - https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_for_publication.pdf

8 ANNEXES

8.1 Minutes of the “stakeHolders2cO-design!” workshop held in Brussels on 17th October 2023

stakeHolders2cO-design! Towards impactful stakeholder engagement in the Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters

INTRODUCTION

Kinnie De Beule, Blue Cluster, introduction

The aim of this workshop is to finetune stakeholder engagement methodologies and their accuracy for the Mission Ocean while gathering valuable input of key experts, as well as to put all participants in contact with the relevant European network and provide with examples. Panellists will share their experience in implementing relevant stakeholder engagement methodologies and identify best practices, successes and challenges, proposing how to effectively “engage, connect and empower” stakeholders within the Mission Ocean & Waters. The second part of the workshop deals with the experiences so far with the regional smart specialization strategies, the third part serves to finetune the stakeholder engagement methodology assessment tool for the mission Oceans, Seas and Waters.

Marijn Rabaut, Blue Cluster, Mission Ocean and PREP4BLUE introduction; Sustainable Blue Economy, from Blue Cluster and working with stakeholders.

[Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”](#), the new Horizon Europe Programme for 2021-2027 is articulated around five missions, targeting the main challenges where research and innovation efforts should be concentrated. The Mission Ocean and Waters aims to restore our oceans, seas and waters by 2030, through the achievement of three main objectives:

- 1) Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity
- 2) Prevent and eliminate pollution
- 3) Make the sustainable blue economy carbon neutral and circular

The implementation of the Mission is supported by transversal actions or “cross-cutting enablers” that will provide access to a digital ocean and water knowledge system (digital twin of the ocean) and guarantee broad public mobilisation and engagement throughout the implementation of the Mission.

The Mission goes beyond research and innovation and will create new forms of governance and ways to connect with the citizens. The four Mission lighthouses will act as hubs where innovative solutions will be developed, demonstrated and deployed in each basin: Atlantic-Arctic, Danube, Mediterranean, Baltic and North Sea.

The Mission will be implemented in 2 phases. The first phase of implementation (2021-2025) will set-up a dynamic ecosystem to boost the creation of innovative solutions of all forms in the lighthouses. The second phase ‘deployment and upscaling’ (2026-2030) will consist of supporting the transfer, uptake and upscale of R&I solutions developed in the first phase of the Mission.

PREP4BLUE is the first coordination and support action project of the Mission Ocean, seas and waters, with the overarching objective to facilitate a successful implementation of the first phase of the Mission Ocean & Waters (2022-2025) by developing the co-creation and co-implementation of R&I modalities required to achieve the Mission objectives and preparing the ground for inspiring and engaging citizens and stakeholders.

The project will deliver relevant recommendations and methodologies on stakeholder engagement. The project team is notably mapping and assessing multidisciplinary, multi-stakeholder strategies involving industry, public authorities, citizens, academia and associations while envisaging the natural environment as key for social innovation and to efficiently bring society closer to the ocean. In the framework of these activities, [Blue Cluster](#), in collaboration with the CPMR organizes this workshop on 17 October 2023.

The presentation of the First Mission arena will be in Gothenburg (14-16 November) for the Nordic countries, for the Belgium and the Netherlands, please save the date on 23 May 2024, in Ostend for the kick-off.

www.bluecluster.be

PART A, the challenge of Stakeholder engagement in the Mission Oceans

The first session gathers experts on stakeholder engagement that contributed to a reflection on how to engage a wide range of stakeholders in research and actual projects and that implemented relevant projects with a strong multi stakeholder co-creation approach. Each speaker will cover one specific aspect of the Mission Ocean and Waters: biodiversity, sustainable blue economy and marine pollution.

- **Matthew Smith**, Ecosystems and Natural Capital Manager, at the JNCC – Joint Nature Conservation Committee, is the co-Author of BiodivERSA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook (2008), providing best practice guidelines for stakeholder engagement in research projects on biodiversity and ecosystem services.

How to bring society closer to the ocean and biodiversity. Pitfalls and opportunities of methodology selection

The **handbook of effective stakeholder engagement** promotes cross cutting interdisciplinarity, integration of actors, delivery of academic excellence, improvement of societal impact, support for researchers conducting SHE and inclusivity in SHE, enhanced legitimacy societal relevance, visibility of research/EU investments, assurance that SHE keeps on going until the end of the projects.

Getting an agreement on complex issues is not straightforward: consider methods and available tools, communicate decisions and outcomes.

What do define: why to engage; who you choose; how to engage them; when you engage them; identify and manage conflict; review, assess and report.

SHE-Credible-Relevant-Legitimate (CReLe)

- **Credibility:** transparency, define objectives, maintain relations and build trust thought the life cycle.
- **Relevance:** usefulness of SHE and outcomes. Understandable languages, respect of timing, identification and planning, assure the impact is real.
- **Legitimacy:** perceived fairness, balanced SH participation, recognize conflict inherent/valuable, manage conflict and dissent.

Key points for effective SHE: engage SH as equal, value all shared knowledge, understand different needs, manage expectations, avoid complexity, provide feedback, address ethical issues

– i.e., IP, GDPR, consider sharing course of research, given the opportunity for SH to plan own engagement.

Reasons & opportunity for SHE: raise awareness, help with achieving objectives, risk management, share best practice, reduce conflict with transparency, access to resources and information, help to understand where different gaps are.

Consider the background & context of SHE before starting.

Identifying SH: identify, assess and engage; ask yourself who is responsible for decision making, who is being affected, who is interested, who has received previous engagement, who is crucial to deliver long term results, who are the most interested/relevant for your work. In defining the SH roles and contributions, it's also important **when:** before, if they are relevant during the developing strategy (to define concept and, identify outcomes); during in helping establishing agreements, for resources provision, to define project planning, for training and capacity building, to help share knowledge, for the scenario development, to co-design conflict resolution and review success measurement; after to define and develop how you want to implement, publicize and promote the results. It is fundamental to **plan the engagement early on.**

Methods for SHE: opening up, exploring, deciding upon the prioritization of key interests. A detailed planning of the program is the key: targeted activities, do not underestimate the cost and time for SHE, gather early feedback, maintain SH interest, focus on influential SH.

Practicalities, Feasibility, Implementation: consider time, and have a plan B.

Manage SH conflicts: open, hidden, latent, well defined, fuzzy or ill defined. Consider different types of SH conflicts as they can be cognitive, from different interests, normative, relationships, needs, processes or structural issues.

Benefits of monitoring and evaluating the conflicts: better planning of SHE, focus on the objectives, measure success and how to do bring more values and benefits, help informing, changing, improving, demonstrate value of money, show SH their contribution's impact. Monitor success, process and impact.

Open-Source Handbook: <https://www.biodiversa.eu/library/#1>

1. Matthew Smith underlines that, regarding the inclusivity and 'leaving no one behind principle' it can happen that someone feels left behind. To avoid this, it is recommended to conduct a proper stakeholder analysis to know who is participating. Communication staff is crucial even in the scientific community. As well, public/social services can help to look for the right SH to be targeted, and SH can also look for other SH. Matthew suggests, to counteract stakeholder fatigue, to identify and choose the real interested SH: reach them and ask why they're not engaged, identify who is not involved, how to bring their views in, involve and open the debate even if they disagree, highlighting the events that are publicly funded. A few years ago, industries operated in the watersheds, and a few years back they noticed that everything is connected. But should we now always involve everyone? Not necessarily. To be sure not to duplicate, you need a clear structure prepared and a strong communication plane: SH value being engaged, but they fear bad or not

worthy engagement. We also need to be aware of the legal framework in which we are operating (data access, intellectual property) since the beginning.

- **Timothy Vanagt**, senior project manager at [ORG](#), presents a relevant example of a co-creative design of large-scale maritime infrastructures in marine environment.

Co-creative design of large-scale projects. Infrastructures in marine environment: stakeholder involvement and carbon neutrality

ORG applies co-creation methodologies through different projects:

- **energy island**, build an artificial island to produce energy but also protect biodiversity. The co-creation process consists of “work benches”: clients and SH receive homework, and it’s a cycle where everybody co-creates and take ownership eventually.

A group of small top experts were selected (not retributed) to work in the project, and ambitions and boundary conditions were set together. Then, for the setting of evaluation criteria, the process of joint fact finding started: the scope was to create a safe space where everything is questioned and should be proved, and a common language is used for all experts (i.e., drawings). Then sections were made (everything is asked to experts from different sections, e.g., biologist about biodiversity) and everything gets quantified and shapes are explored (of the island, of the floors etc.). Afterwards, construction methods are explored with clear and transparent zoom-ins. Then a continuous monitoring and evaluating process are set. <https://orgpermod.com/systems/projects/maritime-systems>

- **coastal vision**, with 20 experts. Following same methodologies >100 stakeholders. <https://orgpermod.com/systems/projects/kustvisie>
- **North-C-neutral**, need for AI support to calculate complex trad offs. AI can help with marine spatial plan and at the project level.
- **SOLV**, co-creation process was done before start with the process, all the stakeholders were interviewed; tool to de-risk were used before and during co-creation.

Additionally, ORG believes that SHenG does not always have to start and be embedded in ‘the field’ – it can be various levels of SH that make a project successful, also ‘only’ political and implementation levels. Subjectivity perception can be tackled by proving as much as possible scientifically.

- **Marisa Fernandez**, coordinator of the department ‘control/management of marine environment and resources’ at the [CETMAR](#), focuses on the engagement of stakeholders in activities related to the prevention and mitigation of marine pollution.

Marine pollution prevention and mitigation, focus on stakeholder engagement.

Marisa is an expert in marine pollution, oil and chemical spills and marine litter prevention and removal projects.

Many international, European and regional conventions and legislations set to reduce and prevent marine pollution have been implemented, as well as many Interreg, EU and national funding programs to support the fight against marine pollution.

Since 2009, many projects have started on oil and chemical spills: they tackle different aspects and issues but share the common goal of improving preparedness and response capabilities against oil and chemical spills. As well, for marine litter projects have started since 2007: the shared goal has been to improve capabilities to prevent, monitor and reduce marine litter. There's a need to produce tools, guidelines, and trainings, and to engage SH.

For SHE: the approach is guided by the knowledge of the context, by common sense and pre-existing relationships. It is better if you already have a methodology and tools to replicate, monitor, and transfer.

Key stakeholders & role: different key SH were involved: competent authorities, organizations in charge of monitoring and responding against pollution, regional sea conventions, EU agencies, International Maritime Organization, productive sectors (e.g., fisheries), social actors (e.g. NGOs), representatives of the civil society.

How to involve them: the role in the project (full partners or associated partners, advisory board, invited expert or collaborator) and by specific project communication and transfer actions; when they were involved (from the beginning of the project or during); by asking them for advice, support for dissemination and involvement on training.

Some challenges: initial untrust from governmental agencies, operational agencies, private sector; language issues; difficult to get the involvement of EU and regional organization, keep the interest and engagement and some SH disappointment and fatigue.

Successful stories: Coastguards-Z operational versus academic approaches, engagement of OSPAR, fisherman during marine litter projects, teachers and scholars.

Final remarks:

tackling marine pollution requires the involvements of a wide typology of SH with different roles: it is key to build trust and use appropriate language. Inclusion and the 'let no one behind principle' is tackled depending on the consultation processes, the identification and mapping process is key! To counteract on stakeholder fatigue, Marisa suggests taking into account the dimension of the process dealt with, do not be too ambitious in the scale. The subjectivity perception can be tackled by communicating and discussing on everything.

13.20 – PART B, stakeholder engagement in R&I regional policy: Entrepreneurial Discovery Process – Smart Specialization Strategies

- Justine Brossard, CRPM, introduction

This session notably presents relevant best practices of the engagement of quadruple helix stakeholders in the elaboration and implementation of their regional smart specialization strategies. It provides a reflection on how to boost stakeholder engagement and co-creation in the entrepreneurial discovery process in the context of the S3, through a presentation of the Open Discovery Process.

The entrepreneurial discovery process in the framework of the S3, is a good example of engagement of stakeholders around the topic of innovation. This session offers concrete examples from regional authorities,

one of the key actors of the Mission Ocean, and multistakeholder co-creation models for the elaboration of R&I policies, in addition to the stakeholder engagement processes in research and environmental projects presented during the first session.

- **Francesco Molica**, Economic and Policy Analyst, Joint Research Centre (JRC), European Commission. Presentation of the reflection around the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process.

Presentation of the concept/theoretical approach: From EDP to ODP?

From an economic perspective, there are two important elements: first information gaps in innovation and industrial policies and secondly address coordination failures and encourage knowledge spillovers across the private sector (stimulating more cooperation across private sector). These elements stand from research studies.

What worked in EDP: the strengthened involvement of stakeholders in both innovation policies and regional/national funding strategies (ESIF), make innovation policies more evidence based, positive effects in terms of policy learning and prioritization and improving communication and coordination amongst a broader array of actors – all were a success.

What worked less well in EDP: the quality of the process is in the end very different according to policy capacities, institutions, local cultures and historical experiences with innovation policies, scant participation of civil society and small enterprises, less participation of some actors, lack of skills and resources sometimes prevented actors from meaningful contribution, issues in vertical and horizontal coordination and EDP led in some instance to too many priorities.

Weak/missing dimensions in the EDP: what is missing is the holistic approach to R&I funding, directionality innovation towards addressing long-term societal challenges, continuity of the process to address uncertainty and adjust to emerging needs/information.

From EDP to ODP/EDP+/XYZ: what about the role of public powers: from main actors driving the strategy knowledge brokers and facilitators, priority setting: shift from sectorial/vertical approach to directions of transformative change and challenge-drive approach, mechanisms: need to experiment with formats to deliver deliberative collaboration. As key features of the ODP you may also apply control vs influence; directionalities; working backwards from goals; openness: goals, agendas and boundaries. It is also important to manage expectations.

- **Francisco Pinto**, Senior Public Officer, Azores S3 Support Unit, Regional Directorate of Science and Technology, presents the case of the Azores.

Partnerships for Regional Innovation – Feedback Azores region, as co-leader of the Working Group on the Open Discovery Process and local missions (CHOIRS)

The **region of Azores** is the co-leader of the Partnership for Regional Innovation Working Group 2 on the Open Discovery Process and local missions (CHOIRS). The results from this working group are presented as well as relevant methods used by the region to foster the engagement of quadruple helix stakeholders around the topic of research and innovation in the blue economy and marine conservation issues.

!Open Discovery Process and Local Missions

The Partnerships for Regional Innovation (PRI) are a new complementary approach to place-based innovation policy. They are a response to the urgent call of the European Green Deal to address challenges posed by climate change in ways that strengthen social and territorial cohesion and ensure that Europe thrives in the green and digital economy of the future.

The process aims to test tools to enhance the coordination and directionality of regional, national and EU innovation policies to implement Europe's green and digital transitions and to tackle the innovation divide in the EU, they are:

- Firmly anchored in the EU policy framework, supporting the implementation of the European Green Deal, Horizon Europe, Cohesion policy and NextGenerationEU.
- They seek to accelerate transformative outcomes by introducing local missions to coordinate actions under a single directional logic, exploring broad-ranging policy mixes for system-level innovation.
- Strongly focused on innovation policy, but also covers and inspires industrial, employment, education, and social policies.
- They imply new ways of working across government departments focused on addressing territorial challenges.
- They emphasise on actions with strong transformative potential for innovation strategies.
- They focus on broad stakeholder engagement, multi-level governance, synergies between policies and between funds, social dimension of innovation, innovation for SMEs, and innovation directions that co-benefit economy, society, and environment.

The key objective of the PRI is to strengthen the interconnection of regional and local innovation ecosystems and to reinforce European sustainable value chains and deep-tech sectors.

PRI builds on S3 dynamics, but shifts focus from only R&D and innovation capacities to a wider societal context, thus, involving all the parts of the quintuple helix (university-industry-government-society-environment). PRI additionally seeks to adopt a broad and systemic framing of innovation, recognizing that the levers for transformative change lie not just in science and technology but also in the very design of our production and consumption systems.

While S3 focuses on mobilizing only cohesion policy funding, PRI favours the integration of cohesion funding with other funding sources, including RRP, Horizon Europe and/or national or regional funding linked to territorial goals. PRI also transitions from the EDP (Entrepreneurial discovery process) to the ODP (Open Discovery Process), involving a broader spectrum of stakeholders from different environments and levels, to make a real and sustainable impact on specific needs of countries, regions and citizens. The PRI Pilot Action was launched by the European Commission and the European Committee of the Regions on May 2022. It has the participation of 4 member states, 63 regions, 7 cities and 6 networks. In total, 23 Member States and 74 European Territories are represented.

Activities are tailored to the interests of each participant, and include:

- Thematic workshops;
- Exchanges of good practices;
- In-depth policy reviews with the involvement of external experts;
- Tailored analytical insights and support from JRC staff (e.g., resilience dashboards, complexity analysis).

The main reference document is the "PRI Playbook", developed by the JRC-European Commission with the support of a Scientific Committee of experts.

ODP key features:

- Openness: goals, agendas, boundaries;
- Directionalities: focus on long term societal wellbeing;
- Working backwards from goals;
- Distinction between control and influence.

It includes the ways the EDP process has been implemented in S3 with the addition of new challenge-oriented partnerships with variable sets of stakeholders, according to the goal.

A core objective of the ODP is the establishment of **CHallenge-Oriented Innovation paRtnerships (CHOIRs)**.

- Multi-stakeholder and multi-level (government) partnerships.
- Linked to concrete territorial challenges.
- Challenge-oriented or mission-oriented.
- Emphasis on agreement, co-creation and co-ownership.

Challenges defined in terms of collectively determined and broadly understood goals.

Combination of shared understanding of goals and autonomy about their implementation allow broad stakeholder coalitions to explore multiple pathways, maximizing the chances to achieve the goal.

CHOIRs Key elements:

- (1) Goals: Agreeing on common goals is a key first step. To ensure alignment with European goals, Territorial goals will have to be seen through the lens of the twin green and digital transition;
- (2) Partners: Partly a function of the goal and vice versa. The relevant parts of public and private stakeholders will vary according to the goal;

- (3) Partnership teams: Executive bodies consisting of stakeholders who engage with representatives of different sets of stakeholders, according to the goal, working under a whole-of-society approach;
- (4) Open agendas: Partnership teams co-develop a collective open and dynamically adjusted agenda describing their proposed path for achieving the goal. Stakeholders open their individual agendas in relation to the goal, permitting synergies in the policy mix and sequencing of actions;
- (5) Partnership hubs: Composed solely of public officials from various parts of government. Hubs provide the interfaces with the parts of government that can help accomplish the goals.

Examples in 4 mission actions:

- NAUTILOS Project (<https://www.nautilus-h2020.eu/>);
- SBEP: Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (<http://frct.azores.gov.pt/>);
- AMAR: Learning the Sea of the Azores (<https://www.oma.pt/index.php>);
- MSP4BIO: Integrating Marine Biodiversity Protection and MS (<https://mspAbio.eu/>).

PRI Pilot action WG2 - Open Discovery Process and local missions (CHOIRs)

Responsibilities of Azores as Co-Leading territory:

- Co-organizing meetings and workshops;
- Internal communication within the WG;
- Communication with the Coordination Team.

The development of a sustainable Blue Economy is critical and a "must" for the Azores.

The relatively small dimension and low population of Azores allows the Regional Government and Local authorities to have a good knowledge of all the relevant regional stakeholders in RD&I. The Azores region is already engaged with the S3 Working Group on Sustainable Blue Economy on a first exercise to draft challenges in the sector. The Azores are working on going from ED to ODP, thus, bringing directionality to the process. JRC will launch, in the following months, the PRI Playbook 2.

- Azores will be featured as a case scenario.
- Local missions already being implemented (Sweden and Catalonia) will be part of the best practices showcases.

Examples of stakeholder engagement processes implemented by Azores

- Co-Organization and hosting of the "2023 S3 Summit" (DRCT, ANI, JRC):
 - 1st journey on RIS3 Azores 2022-2027;
 - Innovation and Smart Specialization Forum;
 - PRI learning journey "Co-creating (inter)regional missions";

- RIS3 Azores 2022-2027 Working Groups workshop (over 120 participants in 5 WG):
 - Experiencing ODP in practice;
 - Discussion on possible local challenges and missions;
 - Draft definition of local priority challenges and missions.

Additionally, it is explained what is planned for 2024: an open call in the scope of the Azores 2030 (ERDF), with budget of € 500.000 ca. to, over a period of one year, identify the main regional challenges, propose a set of future calls and propose a set of priority local missions (in-line with EU missions). A new series of RIS3 Azores 2022-2027 WG workshops will be organized.

A Peer Review process was selected, within the scope of Interreg Europe, for a dialogue with stakeholders on the S3\PRI and Local-Regional Missions topic.

- **Astrid Burhoi**, represents the region of Vastra Gotaland (Sweden) present best practices from their respective region in the entrepreneurial discovery process, to engage quadruple helix stakeholders from the blue economy sector in a dialogue on research and innovation.

Best practice of stakeholder engagement in the elaboration of regional smart specialization strategies - Entrepreneurial Discovery Process in Vastra Gotaland

Vastra Gotaland region, is one of the Europe's leading maritime regions with solution focused on innovation and sustainable growth. The first regional strategy was 2008 in dialogue with regional actors and then reviewed in 2015 with the goal to 'go together'. The policy and funding program for Sustainable maritime industries runs from 2016-2020 to help the actors achieve their goals; 7 areas were used for the development. From 2021 the maritime sector is part of Region Vastra Goatland. To build regional and local innovation capacity for a sustainable blue economy, it is required to detect needs and possibilities, engage, and mobilize actors and partnerships and support sustainable innovation and knowledge-based growth. Based on that, an innovative platform (Biable Seas) for a sustainable Blue Economy and regional financial and strategic involvement is underdevelopment. Another project, on sustainable production of fish using AI and advanced data analysis has the aim to enable the land-based fish production.

For **citizens engagement** (5-13 August 2023) the team tried to use data collected during citizens involvement, and to know them part of the process, more involved and aware.

Concluding remarks: It is clear that the long-time perspective is important; more synergies in the maritime area are needed; increased visibility of the sea as a natural resource and ecological system; better collaborative between established industry and start-ups; more regional investments for a living coastal area.

- **Nicolas Dourlens**, representing the region of Occitanie, presents best practices from their respective region in the entrepreneurial discovery process, to engage quadruple helix stakeholders from the blue economy sector in a dialogue on research and innovation.

Best practice of stakeholder engagement in the elaboration of regional smart specialization strategies - Entrepreneurial Discovery Process in Occitanie region

La Région Occitanie Pyrénées – Méditerranée: this region has 220 km of coasts, with the following threats: erosion of the sideline, marine submersion, marine pollution, aging infrastructures, demographic and urban pressure, economic activities to strengthen and develop. A challenge is to be able to reformulate the littoral and maritime territory, to give it a new dimension.

The **role of the region** in innovative process is being a facilitator between research, public policy and business and rely on the regional strategic priorities to create a leverage effect.

In 2022, a study measure economic dynamics of region helping with the identification of several activities composing the Blue Economy and helping the regional economical level to find new financial solutions and be a significant leverage and encourage innovation and propose new solutions recognizing Occitane as a strategic leader.

The tools the region has used are:

- For the Strategic level
 - Smart Specialisation Strategy:
 - Regional scheme for economic development, innovation and internationalization
- For the Civil society
 - Parliament of the Sea: to bring the strategy into line with civil society stakeholders and their needs
- For the businesses
 - Avenir littoral call to attract companies with innovation projects in several themes (2 or 3 themes by edition of the call)
 - Sectors contracts: fishing, boating, aquaculture

The Smart Specialization Strategy was elaborated in 2020 for 7 years (2021-2027) part of regional Green Pact for a sustainable economy and covered 5 topics:

- Floating offshore wind
- Smart & Green boats
- Smart & green Harbours
- Coastal ecological engineering
- Bioresources and blue biotechnologies

Regular working groups with all willing stakeholders on the 5 topics were conducted, with priorities based on expressed needs.

More clarifications: Parliament of the sea, an original structure unites and represents the maritime community, bringing forward projects and new ideas, innovations, best practices, organize dialogue, debate and mutual understanding. Also carries out national and European lobbying. It has three decision levels: a forum (1573 members), an assembly made up of 4 colleges (212 members) and an executive office (20 members).

Covering 5 cross-cutting themes:

- Identity/culture/heritage
- Ecological transition (biodiversity, renewable energy, etc.)
- Blue economy/attractiveness of professions
- Coastal planning/landscape
- Coastal appeal/International relations.

Parliament's Blue Economy Working Group: the main aim is to help Occitanie Region to build and develop blue economy strategy. The first action was done in 2019 with the creation of study specifications about Blue Economy, sharing progress and results. The study was updated in 2022 and a public feedback event will be held in March 2023.

The aim of Blue Occitanie Economy Community is to help Blue Economy actors to scale-up. The regional economic development agency Ad'occ and the Pole mer mediterranée Cluster are supporting the Region in this process:

- Avenir littoral call: defining and sharing annual themes, stakeholder network, project follow up, catalogue.
- Blue Occitanie economy community: webinars dedicated to Blue Economy actors, shared presence at trade fairs.

The regions intend to manage the funds (e.g., for AI) and then the industry can manage the process. Innovation in the regions is conducted through meetings all SH, and with key stakeholder (as universities) organize scheduled meeting. In some regions like the Atlantic most SH are very well known so it is more practical. Networking with different regions and external actors can take time, at the beginning they need some coordination but now they are working in Vasta Gotaland.

8.2 Concept Note outlining a “stakeholder engagement strategy for the Mission Oceans, Seas and Water”

VISION

A collaborative ecosystem is set where stakeholders are actively engaged, connected, and empowered to drive forward the mission Mission of preserving and enhancing our oceans, seas, and waters by 2030.

MAIN OBJECTIVE

Fostering an inclusive and participatory governance approach, promoting active engagement and collaboration among diverse stakeholders - such as governments, environmental organizations, industry leaders, local communities, scientists, and citizens - in the co-design and co-implementation of solutions for restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To create a dynamic and interactive environment where stakeholders are not just passive recipients of information but active contributors to the Mission evolution and success.
2. To create a robust, interactive, and cohesive network of diverse stakeholders.
3. To enable stakeholders towards more active, informed, and influential role in Mission’s projects and initiatives.

KEY STEPS FOR STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

One of the foundations of the mission is the steadfast engagement of stakeholders, realized through a comprehensive strategy. To this end, the first key steps are:

1. Identify and map all potential stakeholders related to the mission.

Mapping the entire landscape of stakeholders ensures a comprehensive understanding that considers all perspectives. This inclusiveness enhances the mission's actions and outcomes: each stakeholder contributes unique assets, from expertise to financial support, and recognizing these strengths is key for optimal resource allocation. Understanding stakeholders also fosters collaboration and unveils synergies, boosting the mission's progress. Their feedback is invaluable in keeping the mission adaptive and relevant. Acknowledging each stakeholder's contribution builds trust and underscores the importance of inclusivity. Moreover, tailoring communication strategies to different stakeholder groups ensures effective information dissemination.

Early identification of stakeholders pre-emptively addresses challenges, saving time and resources. Among them the following challenges can be mentioned:

- **Enhanced Societal Impact:** Involving stakeholders from the beginning ensures that the mission's activities are aligned with societal needs and expectations. This is particularly important for initiatives that require public acceptance or have a direct impact on communities.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Early stakeholder engagement facilitates the incorporation of diverse expertise, including from Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) disciplines. This interdisciplinary approach is essential for understanding and addressing complex environmental and societal issues related to oceans and waters.
- **Effective Decision-Making:** By involving stakeholders early, the mission can benefit from a wide range of perspectives, leading to more informed and effective decision-

making. This can include insights from environmental organizations, NGOs, government agencies, and regional authorities.

- **Proactive Problem-Solving:** Early engagement helps in preemptively identifying potential obstacles and opportunities, allowing for proactive strategies to address them. This can be crucial in complex projects involving multiple interests and potential conflicts.
- **Building Trust and Support:** Early and continuous engagement with stakeholders helps in building trust and securing ongoing support for the mission's activities. It emphasizes inclusivity and demonstrates a commitment to considering and valuing diverse contributions.

Thus, stakeholder identification and engagement in the "Mission Ocean and Waters" can significantly enhance the effectiveness, acceptance, and impact of the mission's activities. The following list outlines specific tasks and considerations in stakeholder identification and mapping:

- a) **Defining System Boundaries:** This initial step involves delineating the system's boundaries, which could be jurisdictional, sectoral, institutional, conceptual, scalar, temporal, or spatial. These boundaries are pivotal in pinpointing relevant stakeholders and serve as the foundational criteria for their inclusion or exclusion in the mapping process. An iterative approach is essential throughout the engagement process, integrating knowledge from various disciplines (ranging from single to transdisciplinary). This integration is particularly valuable in complex environmental contexts, emphasizing the need to understand specific geographic, economic, demographic, and institutional factors for effective stakeholder identification.
- b) **Identifying Stakeholders:** Beginning with the project's network, stakeholder identification should expand to include literature reviews, document analysis, and snowball sampling. Stakeholders are classified according to predetermined groups and roles, representing either individual or societal segments. Engaging stakeholders from diverse disciplines and sectors is crucial, often involving collaborations between academics and non-academics to address natural resource challenges. Additionally, employing semi-structured interviews helps in comprehending stakeholders' perspectives on challenges and potential solutions, aiding in customizing the engagement process to specific needs and contexts. The identification incorporates both internal stakeholders (involved in project execution) and external ones (affected by it), using the "Penta-Helix" model encompassing industry, science, public authorities, citizens, and associations.
- c) **Mapping Stakeholders and Segmentation:** This step employs methods to map stakeholders based on their representation and influence, acknowledging that each stakeholder may embody different roles. Incorporating collaborative methods across disciplines ensures a comprehensive mapping, considering diverse perspectives to prevent overlooking crucial elements and stakeholders. A Collaborative Research Framework (CRF) that blends 'top-down' and 'bottom-up' approaches enriches this mapping. Post-identification, stakeholders are segmented according to their roles, responsibilities, and influence levels, aiding in visualizing the stakeholder ecosystem through mapping.
- d) **Involving Stakeholders in Knowledge Co-Production and Adaptation Strategies:** Assessing each stakeholder's desired and required level of participation is key. This process, which should be iterative, involves determining stakeholder involvement based on their group, role, and impact on the situation. Engagement strategies should focus on creating societally relevant outcomes through a transparent and iterative process, establishing clear roles, and allocating resources effectively. Stakeholders' involvement

should be planned at different project stages, aligning their engagement with goals such as climate resilience, carbon neutrality, and environmental protection.

- e) **Monitoring Involvement:** Monitoring stakeholder involvement throughout the co-creation process is critical due to its resource-intensive nature. Developing robust indicators to assess the impact and effectiveness of co-creation is necessary for identifying improvement areas and best practices. This monitoring process involves evaluating the effectiveness of engagement strategies and addressing knowledge gaps, with stakeholder feedback being vital for refining engagement practices.
- f) **Collaborative Governance and Adaptive Management:** Effective stakeholder engagement requires collaborative governance and adaptive management strategies, focusing on building trust, consensus, conflict resolution, and maintaining transparency and accountability.
- g) **Involving Stakeholders in Decision Making:** Involving stakeholders in decision-making is essential, especially those responsible for decision-making, affected by the project, previously engaged, crucial for long-term results, or representing the most interested/relevant organizations.
- h) **Ongoing Evaluation and Adaptation of Engagement Processes:** Continuously evaluating engagement processes is recommended for developing evidence-based practices. Tailoring engagement to meet the diverse needs of stakeholders at different resource management and decision-making scales is crucial for effective stakeholder engagement.

These tasks provide a comprehensive framework for systematically identifying, mapping, involving, and monitoring stakeholders in the context of environmental and oceanic missions.

2. Foster an environment of open communication and trust.

In the realm of collaboration, especially in initiatives like the "Mission Ocean and Waters," the conditions surrounding the efforts play a crucial role in the success of collective endeavors. Central to this is the establishment of open communication and trust among all involved parties.

Open Communication as a Foundation: Open communication serves as a vital channel for the free exchange of ideas, addressing concerns, and fostering constructive dialogue. It is essential for ensuring inclusivity, where every participant's voice is recognized and valued. This approach helps in reducing uncertainties and aligning all parties towards a common goal. To effectively implement open communication, the following steps are recommended:

- a) **Two-Way Communication Platforms:** two-way communication platforms are seen as beneficial for enabling stakeholders to express their opinions, concerns, and ideas. These platforms could include surveys, public forums, and feedback portals, facilitating interactive dialogue.
- b) **Consistent Updates and Communication Schedule:** Regular updates about the Mission's developments, milestones, and changes, along with a consistent communication schedule, are also considered important for keeping stakeholders continuously engaged and informed.

Trust as the Cornerstone: Concurrently, trust allows parties to engage confidently, share resources, and collectively address challenges. In a trust-rich environment, risks are shared, innovations are pursued collaboratively, and obstacles become opportunities for mutual learning. To foster trust, the following steps should be considered:

- a) **Constructive Conflict Resolution:** A fair and impartial conflict resolution process, respecting all stakeholder perspectives and aiming to constructively resolve conflicts, is often seen as crucial in maintaining this trust.
- b) **Individual Interviews for Deeper Engagement:** Conducting individual interviews rather than group discussions is thought to be effective in addressing power disparities among stakeholders, promoting frankness in responses, and ensuring transparency and consistency in engagement.

Building a Collaborative Infrastructure: Moreover, developing infrastructure that supports collaborative efforts is crucial. Constructing platforms and tools tailored for collaboration, information sharing, and continuous interaction is key. These tools should be designed to simplify complex tasks, facilitate co-creation, and augment shared resources, thereby driving cohesive operations.

Cultivating a Bespoke Collaborative Ambiance: To cultivate such an ambiance, a well-thought-out plan, bespoke to the context and the involved parties, is essential. This includes strategies for clear communication, feedback systems, decision-making transparency, stakeholder involvement, accountability standards, and cultural awareness. By integrating these methodologies, an environment conducive to open dialogue and trust is nurtured, setting the stage for collaborative success.

In summary, the synthesis of open communication, trust-building strategies, individualized engagement, and a supportive collaborative infrastructure forms the backbone of effective stakeholder engagement in the "Mission Ocean and Waters." This comprehensive approach not only addresses logistical aspects but also ensures meaningful, inclusive, and effective stakeholder participation.

3. Drive proactive engagement

Proactivity is the cornerstone of successful stakeholder engagement, especially in the Mission. Driving engagement is not just about reacting to stakeholder needs but anticipating them. To foster proactive engagement of stakeholders, it is essential to implement strategic steps that go beyond the basic identification and mapping of stakeholders. These steps focus on enhancing interaction, understanding, and responsiveness:

- a) **Organizing Consultation Events, Workshops, and Forums:** Creating platforms for stakeholder interaction, learning, and collaboration. These events act as catalysts for discussions and the exchange of innovative ideas, fostering solution-driven dialogues and continuous discourse aligned with the mission's objectives.
- b) **Tailoring Engagement Strategies:** Aligning engagement strategies with the specific interests and needs of different stakeholder groups, using appropriate language and communication channels. Understanding these nuances allows for more effective engagement.
- c) **Responsive Adaptation of Strategies:** Regularly reviewing engagement and communication strategies and being open to adjustments based on stakeholder feedback. This adaptability ensures the engagement process remains relevant and effective.
- d) **Identifying Triggers and Mitigation Measures:** Recognizing that stakeholders may react differently to various project actions and developing appropriate mitigation measures to manage expectations effectively.
- e) **Iterative Assessment of Stakeholder Involvement Levels:** Continuously assessing stakeholders based on their roles, impacts, and willingness to participate, and adjusting engagement as necessary.

- f) **Utilizing a Typology of Participation:** Implementing different levels of participation such as non-participation, low participation (awareness, information, consultation), and high participation (deliberation, co-design, co-decision-making) to manage stakeholder involvement throughout the project lifecycle.
- g) **In-Depth Interviews for Knowledge Co-Production:** Conducting individual, semi-structured interviews to inform empirical research and build relationships, thereby facilitating long-term collaborative research processes.
- h) **Implementing the RILEC Criteria:** Applying Relevance, Inclusion, Learning, Effectiveness, and Credibility criteria for assessing co-creation roles, and regularly monitoring these aspects using qualitative and quantitative methods.
- i) **Formative Evaluation of Engagement:** Using online surveys and other methods to evaluate stakeholders' perceptions, thereby creating a space for learning and knowledge exchange.
- j) **Organic Approach to Engagement Diversity:** Tailoring engagement experiences to specific contexts and work scopes, embracing a diverse range of engagement modalities to address complex resource problems.

KEY STEPS FOR CONNECTING AND EMPOWERING STAKEHOLDERS

Connecting and empowering stakeholders in stakeholder engagement, particularly in the context of marine governance, involves creating a cohesive and comprehensive framework. This framework is designed to build robust networks and ensure stakeholders play an active, influential role in governance. Here's how the operational tasks and aspects can be integrated and streamlined:

1. Connecting Stakeholders:

- a) **Establish Collaborative Governance Structures:**
 - Formulate a strategy involving stakeholders from public, private sectors, and civil society.
 - Embrace diverse viewpoints from varied groups including government, local communities, industry, NGOs, and academia.
 - Utilize multifaceted approaches like Integrated and Adaptive Management, Conflict Resolution, Co-Management, Policy Development, Capacity Building, and Education.
- b) **Foster Diverse Stakeholder Networks:**
 - Engage stakeholders across sectors and regions for a dynamic community.
 - Use stakeholder mapping to identify and unite diverse perspectives.
- c) **Cultivate Partnership Opportunities:**
 - Create partnership opportunities among governmental bodies, private organizations, and environmental groups.
 - Facilitate collaboration on joint projects and co-funding initiatives.
- d) **Implement Effective Communication Strategies:**
 - Maintain transparent communication channels.
 - Utilize various feedback mechanisms and tailor communication to stakeholder groups.
- e) **Utilize Digital Platforms for Engagement:**
 - Leverage digital tools to connect stakeholders regardless of geographical distances.
- f) **Organize Multi-Stakeholder Convergences:**

- Host conferences, seminars, and workshops as platforms for discussion and community building.
 - g) **Encourage Interdisciplinary Collaboration:**
 - Promote collaborations across science, industry, and governance for holistic solutions.
 - h) **Monitor and Evaluate Engagement:**
 - Set measurable objectives for stakeholder engagement and use KPIs for assessment.
2. Empowering Stakeholders:
- a) **Establish Stakeholder Rights and Responsibilities:**
 - Define legal definitions for stakeholder categories, detailing their rights and duties.
 - Develop legal frameworks for transparency and accountability in stakeholder involvement.
 - b) **Collaborative Governance for Decision-Making:**
 - Create multi-stakeholder platforms like task forces or advisory boards for inclusive decision-making.
 - Tackle challenges in collaborative governance such as differing objectives and power imbalances.
 - c) **Integrated Management in Marine Governance:**
 - Adopt holistic management approaches like Ecosystem-Based Management and Marine Spatial Planning.
 - Consider complex interrelationships in marine governance for sustainable resource use.
 - d) **Encourage Shared Management Practices:**
 - Directly involve stakeholders in decision-making, leveraging their local knowledge.
 - Implement co-management strategies for shared responsibility in marine governance.
 - e) **Involve Stakeholders in Policy Processes:**
 - Engage stakeholders throughout policy-making, from identification to implementation.
 - Shape policies with diverse viewpoints for broader acceptance and legitimacy.
 - f) **Capacity Building and Education:**
 - Provide training and knowledge sharing to enhance stakeholders' engagement capabilities.
 - Utilize educational programs to deepen understanding of marine conservation and governance.

According to this process, stakeholders are not only effectively connected but also empowered to actively participate and influence marine governance initiatives. This approach ensures that policies and decisions are informed by a range of perspectives, leading to more resilient and sustainable outcomes.